

Studies in the Synthesis of Thiazolidinones. Part-II*. 5-Benzal Derivatives of 2-(Substituted Benzothiazole-2'-yl-imino)-4-Thiazolidinones and their Brominated Products

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The present investigation describes the synthesis of some 2-(substituted benzothiazole-2'-yl-imino)-4-thiazolidinones, their arylidene derivatives and brominated products. The effect of carbonyl absorption of thiazolidinone and its arylidene derivatives in I.R. region has been studied. The antifungal and antibacterial activities of some of the compounds have also been evaluated.

THIAZOLIDINONES and their derivatives have a significant therapeutic importance¹⁻³. It has also been observed that benzothiazole and their derivatives possess remarkable physiological properties⁴⁻⁶. It was therefore, thought of interest to introduce a benzothiazole ring into a thiazolidinone moiety and also to study the effect of carbonyl absorption in I.R. region by preparing its different arylidene derivatives. Since the introduction of bromine atom augments the bactericidal⁷ and fungicidal⁸ activities of thiazolidinones, the arylidene derivatives have been brominated as possible bactericides and fungicides.

1. C₆H₅CO-CNS, NaOH.
2. Cl.CH₂-COOH, NaOAc and HOAc.
3. R-CHO, NaOAc, HOAc.
4. Br₂, CHCl₃.

The synthesis of thiazolidinones were achieved through the following steps.

(1) Preparation of 2-amino (4 or 6) -substituted benzothiazoles from their respective aryl thioureas by oxidation with bromine.

(2) Conversion of the amino benzothiazoles to benzothiazolyl thioureas(II) by heating them with benzoyl thiocyanate (prepared from ammonium thiocyanate and benzoyl chloride) and hydrolysing the product with sodium hydroxide.

(3) Condensation of benzo-thiazolyl thioureas with monochloro acetic acid in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate to thiazolidinones(III).

The thiazolidinones have been condensed with various aromatic aldehydes and the resulting arylidene derivatives (IV) have been brominated to V; with one bromine atom in the thiazolidinone ring.

Comparison of the carbonyl absorption (Table 1) of the thiazolidinone and its various arylidene derivatives reveals the following interesting conclusions.

(1) There is a bathochromic shift in the carbonyl absorption in case of benzyldene compound because of unsaturation in 5-position.

(2) Electron donating substituents like -OCH₃, -N(CH₃)₂, Cl and -OH in para position of the benzyldene derivatives increases the magnitude of the bathochromic shift as conjugation is favoured.

(3) Electron withdrawing substituents like -NO₂ in para position decreases the shift as conjugation is retarded.

Pharmacological test. The bactericidal and fungicidal tests of some of the compounds were carried out on Assay broth and Sabouraud's broth media respectively. The test results indicate that none of these compounds possess bactericidal activities against *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*, *S. typhi*, and *E. coli* in a concentration of 100 µg/ml. But 2-(benzothiazole-2'-yl-imino) 5-(p-chloro) benzal 4-thiazolidinone and

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its dibromo compound are active against *T. mentagrophytes* and *M. canis* in a concentration of 25µg/ml.

TABLE I. CARBONYL ABSORPTION

Compound	Carbonyl absorption in cm ⁻¹
Thiazoliindone (III, R ₁ = H)	1730
Arylidene derivatives	
(IV, R ₁ and R ₂ = H)	1680
IV; R ₁ = H, R ₂ = <i>p</i> -OCH ₃	1670
IV, R ₁ = H, R ₂ = <i>p</i> -(NO ₂)	1700
IV; R ₁ = H, R ₂ = <i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ N	1670
IV; R ₁ = H, R ₂ = <i>p</i> -Cl	1680
IV; R ₁ = H, R ₂ = <i>p</i> -OH	1670

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected.

I.R. spectra of the compounds were taken on KBr discs, in Perkin Elmer 521 spectrophotometer.

2-Amino benzothiazoles :

Aryl thiourea (0.1M) in a suspension of chloroform was treated with bromine (0.11 M) in chloroform dropwise. It was refluxed on a water bath till HBr is completely removed. Excess of chloroform was removed under reduced pressure and the products were isolated according to Bhargava *et al.*⁹

N'-(Substituted benzothiazole-2-yl) thioureas (II) :

A solution of ammonium thiocyanate (9 g) in acetone (50 ml) was taken inside a three necked flask provided with a reflux condenser, a dropping funnel and a mechanical stirrer. Benzoyl chloride (13 ml) was added dropwise with stirring. After the addition was completed, a solution of 2-amino benzothiazole (0.1 M) in acetone (50 ml) was added dropwise so that the solution was refluxed at its own temperature. The whole reaction mixture was poured into cold water (1 litre) and the resulting yellow precipitate was filtered off and hydrolysed

by boiling with a solution of NaOH (30 g) in water (300 ml). It was filtered and the filtrate was acidified with conc. HCl and made basic with ammonium hydroxide. The solid obtained was filtered, dried and crystallised from alcohol.

The different thioureas prepared as above have been recorded in Table 2.

2-(Benzothiazole-2'-y-limino) 4-thiazolidinone (III, R₁ = H) :

A mixture of benzothiazoyl thiourea (3.15 g) monochloro acetic acid (2 g) and anhydrous sodium acetate (1 g) in ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed over an asbestos centered wire gauze for 5 hrs. Excess of alcohol was distilled off and the residue was treated with water. The solid obtained was filtered, washed several times with hot water, dried and crystallised from alcohol. Yield 80%, m.p. 165°. (Found S, 12.59; N, 16.32. C₁₀H₇N₃OS₂ requires S, 12.85, N, 16.86%). λ_{max} (cm⁻¹). 1405 CH deformation in CH₂, 1650 C = N stretching, 1730 (C = O), 3300 (N-H) broad.

Other substituted thiazolidinones have been reported in Table 2.

2-(Benzothiazole-2'-y-limino) 5-benzal 4-thiazolidinone (IV) ; R₁ and R₂ = H :

A mixture of benzaldehyde (0.11 g), thiazolidinone (III, R₁ = H) (0.25 g) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.5 g) in acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed slowly for 2 hrs. After cooling the solution was poured into cold water and kept overnight. The resulting yellow solid was filtered, washed with hot water, dried and crystallised from alcohol. Yield, 65%, m.p. 231°. (Found : S, 9.12; N, 12.73. C₁₇H₁₁S₂N₃O requires S, 9.49; N, 12.46%). λ_{max} (cm⁻¹) 1650 due to C = N and C = C, 1680 (C = O), 3400 (NH) broad.

Analytical data of substituted arylidene derivatives are in Table 3.

Dibromo derivatives of IV :

To the solution of above arylidene derivative (0.01 M) in chloroform (20 ml), bromine (5 drops) in

TABLE 2

R ₁	Benzothiazoyl thioureas(II)				Thiazolidinones(III)			
	Yield %	M.P. °C	% of Sulphur		Yield %	M.P. °C	% of Sulphur	
			Found	Calcd.			Found	Calcd.
H	83	153	15.20	15.31	80	165	12.59	12.85
6-Cl	80	213	13.23	13.14	80	217	11.16	11.28
6-CH ₃	76	211	14.46	14.35	75	235	12.33	12.16
6-CH ₃ O	70	169	13.06	13.39	70	160	11.59	11.47
6-NO ₂	50	223	12.52	12.60	—	—	—	—
6-C ₂ H ₅ O	70	162	12.39	12.65	—	—	—	—
4-Cl	65	207	13.26	13.14	65	154	11.10	11.28

TABLE 3

Nature of R ₁	Nature of R' ₂	Arylidene Derivatives(IV)				Dibromo Derivatives(V)			
		Yield %	M.P. °C	% of Sulphur		Yield %	M.P. °C	% of Bromine	
				Found	Calcd.			Found	Calcd.
H	H	—	—	—	—	50	239	32.06	32.19
H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	60	179	8.63	8.72	45	238	30.19	30.36
H	<i>o</i> -Cl	60	205	8.51	8.61	45	253	36.36*	36.78
H	<i>p</i> -Br	50	189	7.39	7.69	40	235	41.54	41.67
H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	55	251	8.20	8.37	45	246	29.39	29.52
H	<i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ N	45	182	8.36	8.42	—	—	—	—
H	<i>o</i> -OH	50	165	9.18	9.06	—	—	—	—
6-CH ₃	H	60	203	9.29	9.12	50	138	31.16	31.31
-do-	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	60	206	8.25	8.40	45	129	29.23	29.56
-do-	<i>o</i> -Cl	60	228	8.41	8.30	45	184	35.61*	35.83
-do-	<i>p</i> -Br.	50	207	7.39	7.40	40	202	40.19	40.67
-do-	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	55	222	8.17	8.08	40	250	28.37	28.77
-do-	<i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ N	50	205	8.03	8.12	—	—	—	—
-do-	<i>o</i> -OH	50	162	8.61	8.72	—	—	—	—
6-Cl	H	55	245	8.37	8.61	60	246	36.60*	36.78
-do-	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	60	218	7.51	7.97	60	209	34.19*	34.81
-do-	<i>o</i> -Cl	55	252	7.49	7.88	55	239	40.31*	40.11
-do-	<i>p</i> -Br.	60	262	7.21	7.10	50	250	45.10*	45.12
-do-	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	50	257	7.50	7.68	50	152	33.76*	33.90
-do-	<i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ N	50	212	7.31	7.72	—	—	—	—
-do-	<i>o</i> -OH	45	209	8.19	8.26	—	—	—	—
6-OCH ₃	H	60	165	8.64	8.72	45	148	30.13	30.36
-do-	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	55	148	8.32	8.06	40	171	28.68	28.72
-do-	<i>o</i> -Cl	53	176	7.81	7.97	42	183	34.40*	34.81
-do-	<i>p</i> -Br.	50	146	7.13	7.17	40	185	39.39	39.60
-do-	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	55	243	7.61	7.77	45	244	27.31	27.97
-do-	<i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ N	50	132	7.50	7.80	—	—	—	—
-do-	<i>o</i> -OH	55	154	8.19	8.35	—	—	—	—
4-Cl	H	50	140	8.33	8.61	40	131	36.51*	36.78
-do-	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	48	170	7.67	7.97	45	178	34.63*	34.81
-do-	<i>o</i> -Cl	45	136	7.62	7.88	45	185	40.10*	40.11
-do-	<i>p</i> -Br.	40	130	7.23	7.10	40	183	45.36*	45.12
-do-	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	45	153	7.42	7.68	40	183	33.65*	33.90
-do-	<i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ N	40	218	7.46	7.72	—	—	—	—
-do-	<i>o</i> -OH	50	172	8.19	8.26	—	—	—	—

+ Indicate halogen content.

chloroform (5 ml) was added at 0° and kept overnight. Chloroform was removed under reduced pressure and SO₂ gas was passed to the aqueous suspension of the residue. The resulting pale yellow solid obtained was filtered, washed with ether and dried and they have been recorded in Table 3.

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